

METHODS OF TEACHING THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE AS FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *Currently, methodology is a special subject, independent science. Based on this, Soviet and advanced scientists in foreign countries formulate specific concepts of the methodology teaching a foreign language, its categories, laws, terms, and tasks. The methodology for teaching Russian as a foreign language has taken shape as an independent academic discipline. There is a fairly extensive literature on teaching Russian as a foreign language.*

Keywords: *methods of teaching a foreign language, its categories, laws, terms, tasks.*

Introduction.

Methods of teaching Russian to foreigners, like any other methodology are based on conclusions and generalizations of a number of sciences, primarily linguistics, didactics, and psychology. Findings from linguistics, psychology, and didactics form the scientific basis of the methods of teaching the Russian language to foreigners.

Just as grammar and words are crucial in teaching a language, the right methodology is the main factor in teaching this language.

Teaching methods depend on different learning goals and conditions, i.e. from non-linguistic factors.

The subject of the methodology is teaching the Russian language as a means of communication- defines the ultimate goal - "to master the language."

Teaching Russian as a foreign language (and any language in general) subject) is a joint activity of the teacher and students.

For students to master the language, the teacher must implement certain educational (teaching) actions: explain new material, give tasks, ask a question check the correctness of the answer, etc. Students should also be active and exercise during the course process a series of actions: read the text, learn words, perform exercises, answer the teacher's questions, etc.

In conventional forms of learning (face-to-face), student actions are always determined and directed by the teacher. She is the one who decides what is needed by the students, at what point, in what sequence, and for what purpose. And, of course, he determines what and how to do in class (even outside of class) yourself. He both directly teaches and teaches students how to learn. But anyone the teacher knows that the teacher's teaching actions do not always give the desired result.

It is necessary to explain to him what methods, and techniques he should use, how to combine them, and how to behave in the audience to achieve the desired goal.

In other words, you need to teach him to consciously manage his learning process, including consciously organizing your learning activities so that the learning process gives us better results.

The subject of methods of teaching Russian as a foreign language is an educational process management system, i.e. system aimed at the most effective acquisition of Russian by students.

Teaching Russian even in the absence of a language environment is understood as learning to speak, communicate, and express thoughts in the Russian language. Thus, the technique has its

subject of research, not repeatable in any of the sciences - teaching another language as a means of communication. This category determines the content of the entire educational process, types of speech activity that must be mastered, and levels of language proficiency that must be achieved in each of these types.

The basic science for the methodology is linguistics (linguistics). Teaching practice shows that not every way of describing the Russian language is equally effective when it comes to teaching foreigners. Without participation linguistics also cannot make teaching effective.

Pedagogical factors should also be taken into account in the educational process. Among them are phenomena and patterns that are studied by general pedagogy. For example, the connection between training and education.

This is especially important when teaching the Russian language - a country where more than 120 nationalities live.

Didactics is a department of pedagogy that sets out general teaching methods. Didactic - instructiveness.

Teaching is a joint activity between teachers and students. Now it is necessary to clarify what has been said: learning is a joint active cognitive activity organized, motivated, and controlled by the teacher. Let's understand this definition and at the same time formulate the most important didactic principles.

1. What is a "joint" activity? As already noted, the teacher and students strive for one common goal. To achieve it, both the teacher and students must perform certain actions. The teacher is obliged to ensure that students do everything they need to do in the right way sequences with the desired effect. Therefore, one of the main didactic principles is the principle of collectivity.

2. The second is the principle of activity. For training to be effective, it is the students who must show initiative, be able to independently and approach the subject creatively, and be able to work independently in and out of class. Ensuring and organizing student activity is the most important task teacher.

3. Didactics suggests how to ensure this activity. Before students should be given a problem to solve the knowledge, skills, and abilities that are included in the curriculum are required. All learning should turn into solving a series of problems that must constantly become more complicated. This is required by the didactic principle of problematicity.

When we teach foreigners the Russian language, here first of all communication problems arise: how to communicate in one or another situation, on this or that topic, etc. When a student feels the need to solve such a problem, he will easily use those words and grammatical structures that we introduced him to in class.

4. What does "feels the need" mean? This means that by itself the problem posed to the student does not yet ensure his activity. There must be a need to solve this problem, i.e. must be created appropriate motivation. The motivating function of the teacher is the most important. The principle of motivation or the principle of motivation is a special didactic principle. A man studying a foreign language is not just for using it to communicate. Students' activities in language acquisition from the psychological side –typical cognitive activity: as a result, students enrich themselves - their consciousness, their personality, and their activity.

5. One of the important didactic principles is the principle of developmental training. When teaching a foreign language, it means what we should ask students in a certain sequence of

increasingly complex communication and cognitive tasks. Need to mark, that not every problem is didactically valuable and causes the student motivated attitude towards it.

All the above principles of any training must be implemented in the methodology of a specific subject, in our case in the methodology of teaching Russian as a foreign language. All of the above principles are interconnected and suggest a very specific model educational process.

Communication is a type of activity. Activities can be not only communicative: there are work activities, cognitive (educational), and gaming but it always has a fundamentally unified psychological structure, which means that the laws of its formation are also the same. From here it follows that both communication and training in such communication must be subject to general psychological patterns.

When a person begins any activity, he has a conscious goal (he knows what he wants to achieve), and there is a motive (i.e. need to achieve this goal). For example, if you want to master the Russian language - this is the target. The motives here can be very different: business (high salary, position in the company), socio-cultural (interest in Russian literature, Russian history, etc.), educational (reading literature in Russian language by specialty), etc. The act of activity begins with the appearance of a goal and the desire to achieve it (motive) and ends when the motive is satisfied, i.e. goal achieved.

Orientation is important in communication. When the teacher first arrives in the audience, he needs to collect as much information as possible about listeners. After orientation, the second phase of activity begins - planning, then implementing the plan - the actual action. And finally, the last phase is monitoring the effectiveness of activities.

Conclusion.

Thus, teaching Russian as a foreign language involves the implementation of several pedagogical approaches that determine the choice of specific methods, techniques, and forms of learning. It is also worth noting the important function of the Russian teacher which becomes student a guide to the world of centuries-old Russian culture, which is reflected in the exact and vibrant Russian words. Correctly chosen methods help not only the learner to master well but also the teacher to provide effective education in imparting knowledge.

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